

Schmidt Ocean Institute Post Expedition Report

Health Diagnostics of Deep-Sea Coral

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Table of contents

1 Overview	2
1.1 Expedition Overview	3
1.2 Authorizations and Permitting.....	3
1.3 Expedition Timeline.....	3
1.4 Expedition Objectives.....	4
2 Expedition Accomplishments	4
2.1 At-sea Accomplishments.....	4
2.1.1 Science	4
2.2 Post-expedition Activities and Accomplishments.....	5
2.2.1 Overview	5
2.2.2 New Discoveries.....	6
2.2.3 Software Utilized.....	8
2.3 Data	8
2.4 Publications	9
3 Appendix	9
3.1 Science Party Information.....	9
3.2 Conferences/Presentations/Posters	10
3.3 Student Projects, Thesis, and Dissertations.....	10
3.4 Cruise Records.....	10
3.5 Media	11
3.6 Community Outreach	11

1 Overview

SOI Expedition ID	FKt230417
Vessel	R/V <i>Falkor (too)</i>
Expedition Name	Health Diagnostics of Deep-Sea Coral
Expedition Dates	2023/04/17 - 2023/5/06
Departure Port	San Juan, Puerto Rico
Termination Port	San Juan, Puerto Rico
Ocean	Atlantic Ocean

Map of Expedition Location

Figure 1: Map of Expedition Location.

1.1 Expedition Overview

Corals play a foundational role in deep-sea ecosystems by providing habitats where invertebrate and fish communities can thrive. Despite their importance in deep-sea ecosystems, there is limited understanding of the controls on and signatures of coral health. This cruise sought to gain a better understanding of coral diversity, distributions, and health within mesophotic and deep-sea habitats off the coast of Puerto Rico.

A central component of the cruise was measuring reactive oxygen species (ROS). ROS are short-lived chemicals that all living organisms create, spanning bacteria to humans. ROS play essential roles in the physiology of life, including nutrient acquisition, pathogen defense, and wound repair. Paradoxically, ROS are both beneficial and detrimental to life. While ROS are essential for basic physiological functions, high concentrations lead to detrimental or, at times, fatal consequences.

Little is known about the production of ROS within corals. While intracellular ROS has been implicated in bleaching and stress in corals, extracellular ROS is more complicated. Many shallow-water corals produce high concentrations of the ROS superoxide extracellularly. Interestingly, corals known to have higher resilience to stress produce significantly higher concentrations of superoxide outside their colonies. Similarly, the production of the ROS hydrogen peroxide has been linked to prey acquisition in some coral species. Yet, due to their short lifetimes (seconds to minutes), little is known about the production of ROS and its function in the ocean, especially below the photic zone (i.e., below SCUBA-diver depth). To address this knowledge gap, the team developed SOLARIS – the first sensor for measuring ROS within the deep-sea. During the first deployment of SOLARIS, the team made the first measurement of superoxide in the deep sea, where they found surprisingly high concentrations associated with some coral species.

This expedition aimed to build on those preliminary findings by conducting detailed investigations of superoxide production as a function of depth, species, and environmental conditions. This research sought to greatly expand the understanding of the role of ROS in the function and health of corals within the widespread mesophotic and deep-sea coral gardens surrounding Puerto Rico.

1.2 Authorizations and Permitting

Permit Number	Permit Authority	Permit Focus
2023-IC-019 (O-VS-PVS15-SJ-01351-01022023)	Gobierno de Puerto Rico, Dept. de Recursos Naturales y Ambientales	Research activities

1.3 Expedition Timeline

The expedition commenced on April 17, 2023, departing from San Juan, Puerto Rico, and returned to San Juan, Puerto Rico, on May 6, 2023.

1.4 Expedition Objectives

The expedition had three primary objectives.

- (1) Explore the waters surrounding Puerto Rico to assess the overall productivity, biodiversity, and health of deep-sea corals.
- (2) Test two newly developed instruments designed to measure reactive oxygen species (ROS) in situ: the Diver-operated Submersible Chemiluminescent Sensor (DISCO) for shallow depths and laboratory measurements, and the Submersible Oceanic Luminescent Analyzer of Reactive Intermediate Species (SOLARIS), an instrument mounted onto ROV *SuBastian* for deeper deployments.
- (3) Evaluate ROS concentrations and production in corals situated along biogeochemical gradients, and to investigate how these measurements relate to ecological, physiological, and evolutionary processes.

2 Expedition Accomplishments

2.1 At-sea Accomplishments

2.1.1 Science

One surprising finding from this expedition was the abundance and diversity of corals at this location. Puerto Rican waters in this region have low nutrients and productivity, yet, the team discovered a wide diversity of corals and sponges at depths spanning the mesophotic to deep-sea. The ability of corals to thrive, despite the low nutrients, raises exciting new questions about how corals may allocate energy resources in relation to their surroundings.

Another exciting finding was the discovery of new species of black corals (see below).

The new sensor, SOLARIS, was used to conduct the first systematic and targeted investigation of ROS production associated with mesophotic and deep-sea corals. The sensor design was based on a handheld version, called DISCO. Dr. Hansel and a team from Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (WHOI) developed both devices, and Schmidt Marine Technology Partners funded the initial development of DISCO.

The research team explored several locations in the waters off Puerto Rico with ROV *SuBastian*, including Whiting Bank, Desecheo Ridge, and Esperanza Ridge. They successfully measured high ROS levels from an *Aplysina* sponge and documented the first observation of extracellular ROS production by a black coral. This data could help scientists better understand how these deep-sea corals react to human activity and changing ocean conditions.

One of the most surprising findings was the contrast between the measurements from corals in Puerto Rico and measurements from deep-sea corals in the Pacific Ocean. In October 2019, high concentrations of extracellular superoxide associated with a variety of corals and sponges were measured on Davidson Seamount in the Monterey Bay National Marine Sanctuary. In Puerto Rico, the concentrations of superoxide were significantly lower and many times non-detectable. Species that were found to have high concentrations (nM) in Monterey Bay (e.g., *Swiftia*), had much lower concentrations (pM) in Puerto Rico.

There could be several possibilities for these differences that justify further investigation. For instance, the difference could be due to the time of year – the measurements in Monterey were in the Fall, while these were made in the Spring in Puerto Rico. Coral activity and productivity have seasonal cycles, and a previous study revealed that corals in Monterey Bay for instance, were metabolically active in the Fall, but senesced in the Spring. Puerto Rican waters are much less productive as well, which could result in slower metabolic rates overall and correspondingly lower ROS production. Alternatively, these differences could point to underlying differences in the health of the corals between the two locations. Follow up data collection and measurements are needed to tease out the underlying reasons.

2.2 Post-expedition Activities and Accomplishments

2.2.1 Overview

Following the expedition, the research team conducted a coordinated set of laboratory, genomic, and taxonomic activities to convert the environmental samples and biological collections into validated biodiversity baselines, strengthened reference resources, and formal discoveries. A variety of post-expedition activities took place at WHOI, Lehigh University, the University of Puerto Rico (UPR), and the Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History (NMNH).

A summary of the activities is as follows:

The WHOI team conducted chemical and biological analyses on water, sponge, and coral samples collected during the cruise. Chemical analysis included measurements of the concentration and isotopic composition of nitrate and ammonia from waters collected inside and outside of barrel sponges. The sponges included several depths and those that were confirmed to be either pumping or not via in situ dye additions. The team also measured dissolved organic nitrogen (DON) within and outside the sponges. DNA was extracted and sequenced from paired samples of sponge tissues (8 sponges and isotope pairs in total). The team also extracted, sequenced, and analyzed DNA from 13 siliceous sponges, including 9 hexactinellids and 4 demosponges. The UPR team measured nutrients (phosphate, nitrate, nitrite, ammonium, silicate) from water samples collected within and outside barrel sponges.

The research team at Lehigh University purified DNA from all eDNA samples collected during the cruise, including both high-volume in situ water samples filtered by the *SuBastian*-mounted device and small-volume samples collected with Niskin bottles. These extracts have been sequenced using marker panels targeting corals, fishes, and a broad eukaryotic marker to enable cross-taxon community assessments. A central analytical outcome is that high-volume, in situ filtration captured more than four times the diversity detected by small-volume Niskins, demonstrating that sampling volume and method can strongly shape biodiversity inference in deep, low-biomass environments. These results form the foundation for two manuscripts that synthesize the eDNA method comparison and the resulting biodiversity patterns across the expedition's sites.

In parallel, Lehigh researchers working with the Smithsonian NMNH generated genome-skimming data for the coral voucher specimens collected during the expedition. These genome skims are being used to build a taxonomically verified reference library that directly improves

classification of eDNA sequences from the same region and habitats, reducing ambiguity and increasing confidence in molecular detections. This integration of curated physical vouchers with genomic reference data is a key step that transforms eDNA from a “signal of presence” into a scalable monitoring tool, because it anchors molecular detections to specimen-backed taxonomy and regional genetic diversity. These genome-skimming data and associated analyses are being assembled into a manuscript currently in review.

Smithsonian NMNH researchers curated the expedition’s voucher specimens, providing taxonomic identifications, and advancing formal descriptions of biodiversity, including new species and higher-order taxonomic groups where warranted. This work ensures that the expedition’s collections have long-term value beyond immediate analyses: curated museum vouchers, accompanied by expert identifications and modern genomic resources, become durable reference points for future ecological studies, comparative systematics, and monitoring programs. The combination of specimen curation and taxonomic description is particularly important in deep-sea coral ecosystems, where undocumented diversity remains common and where management decisions often must be made with incomplete baseline information.

Collectively, these post-expedition activities produced outcomes with direct significance for policymakers, local communities, and the broader scientific community. For policymakers and resource managers, the clear performance difference between high-volume in situ eDNA sampling and small-volume Niskin sampling provides evidence to refine best practices for deep-sea biodiversity assessment, strengthening the reliability of environmental baselines used in spatial planning, impact assessment, and long-term monitoring of vulnerable coral habitats. For local communities, the work improves the ability to document and track deep-sea biodiversity that constitutes part of the region’s natural heritage, supporting stewardship with data products that are more complete and less biased by undersampling. For the scientific community, the project contributes both methodological advances (demonstrating how sampling design influences detectability and how genome-informed reference libraries improve eDNA classification) and foundational biodiversity knowledge through curated vouchers, genomic resources, and formal taxonomic discoveries that will continue to enable research well beyond the original expedition.

2.2.2 New Discoveries

New Controls on Coral ROS Production

This research led to several discoveries about ROS production in the deep-sea. First, the first measurement of superoxide production by black corals was made. Second, the contrast between the high superoxide measured associated with corals in the Pacific compared to the corals here point to geographic and/or seasonal controls on coral ROS production. Lastly, the performance of the deep-sea sensor was validated and essential modifications to improve future measurements were identified.

New Sources of Antimicrobials

As part of the research exploring ROS production by sponges, DNA analyses revealed surprisingly high diversity of biosynthetic gene clusters – sets of genes that produce essential secondary metabolites including antimicrobials. (*Lane et al., in progress*)

Unique Sponge-Microbiome Relationships

Siliceous sponges remain a poorly investigated group of marine organisms. The research here found a wide diversity of microbes associated with mesophotic and deep-sea sponges. Surprisingly, the microbiome of one deep-sea sponge is nearly entirely composed on one microbe – an ammonia-oxidizing archaea – pointing to the essential role of the microbiome in N assimilation in sponges. (Lane *et al*, in review)

New Species Discovered

Ameripathes pseudomyriophylla (Horowitz *et al.* 2024)

The researchers discovered and described a new family, genus, and species of black corals, anchored by a holotype from east of Desecheo Island, Puerto Rico (165 m), collected on the expedition. The species is also tied to additional historical material spanning the wider Caribbean/Gulf region, indicating a broader but previously unrecognized distribution for this lineage.

The species is only known from the Caribbean and the Gulf of Mexico between 54-532 m depth. The study leveraged robust molecular data to navigate the complexities of classification especially when the new species shared branching, spine, and polyp characteristics with families Myriopathidae & Stylopathidae. By integrating detailed morphological examinations with advanced molecular analyses, the research confidently positions the new species within a novel genus and family. The species name is derived from pseud (false) and myriophylla in reference to the very similar appearance to species in the genus Myripathes with M. myriophylla being the type species of the genus. This is a major discovery, as it identifies a previously unrecognized deep evolutionary lineage within Antipatharia and provides a clearer, genomics-supported framework for identifying similar corals.

Stauropathes monopinnata (Horowitz *et al.* 2025)

A new black coral species was described based on specimens from Whiting Bank, Puerto Rico (738 m) and near Midway Atoll, Hawai'i (1604 m), supported by both morphology and a large nuclear-locus phylogeny. The discovery expands known diversity within Schizopathidae and clarifies how “look-alike” colony forms can mask distinct evolutionary lineages. The most prominent difference is that the new species is unbranched whereas other species are branched. The new species also has wider distances between pinnules in a row. Known from North Central Atlantic Ocean to North Pacific Ocean from 738-1604 m depth. The name derives from the Latin “mono” (one) and “Pinnata” (feathered) referring to the new species general appearance due to the distinctive lack of branches compared to the other species in the genus. The discovery adds confirmed biodiversity from deep habitats and shows how modern genomic tools help avoid misidentifying distinct species that share similar colony forms.

Pseudomadrepora Vaga *et al.* (2025)

The study described a new coral genus, *Pseudomadrepora*, with *Pseudomadrepora carolina* as the type species (a new combination), based on strong genomic evidence that it is not a true *Madrepora* relative. This corrects a long-standing classification error driven by skeletal

resemblance and improves evolutionary and biodiversity mapping for deep/azooxanthellate corals.

Dorymenia gummi (Cobo et al. 2025)

A new species of solenogaster mollusks collected east of Puerto Rico at ~1458 m, with type material deposited at Smithsonian NMNH and supported by DNA barcodes. ROV observations show it living on a specific octocoral host (a *Sibogorgia* colony), underscoring that host-associated deep-sea invertebrate diversity is still being actively uncovered.

Strophomenia boricua (Cobo et al. 2025)

This new solenogaster species was discovered **off western Puerto Rico at 389 m**, with multiple individuals observed on branches of a *Villogorgia* colony in ROV imagery. The publication highlights how coral-host associations (here, *Villogorgia nigrescens*) can be informative for delimiting species in groups where anatomy alone can be ambiguous.

Hyalonematidae sp.

One sponge sample analyzed via spicule and DNA analysis appears to be a new species (possibly genus). This analysis is still underway in collaboration with sponge scientists at the Smithsonian NMNH.

2.2.3 Software Utilized

A variety of software was utilized for chemical and biological measurements and analysis, including:

- DNA analysis: BBDuk, FastQC, Megahit, Metabat2, GTDBTK, Prodigal, METABOLIC-C, SILVA, fastp, phyloFlash, SPAdes, Bowtie2, MAFFT, RAxML, iTOL, among others.
- Statistical analysis: various R packages, including vegan, pairwiseAdonis
- Figures: various Python packages, ggplot, and Matlab
- Chemical analysis: various custom scripts in Visual Basic, IonVantage, and Excel

2.3 Data

Datasets acquired during this expedition and those derived from the analysis of collected data and samples as of this report's publication date.

Data Type	Curator	Status
Vessel underway data (CTD, Mutlibeam sonar, etc.)	Rolling Deck to Repository	Completed
ADCP	University of Hawaii Data Acquisition System	Completed
Processed multibeam sonar	Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS)	Completed
Raw amplicon sequences – Corals and Sponges	GenBank/NCBI	Completed

2.4 Publications

Horowitz, J., Opresko, D., Herrera, S., Hansel, C., Quattrini, A. (2024). Ameripathidae, a new family of antipatharian corals (Cnidaria, Anthozoa, Hexacorallia, Antipatharia). *Zookeys*, doi: 10.3897/zookeys.1203.121411.

Horowitz, J., Barajas, M., McCartin, L., Vohsen, S., Herrera, S. (2025). Description of a new species of *Stauropathes* (Anthozoa, Antipatharia, Schizopathidae) from Puerto Rico, *Zookeys*, doi: 10.3897/zookeys.1231.136967.

McCartin, L.J., S.A. Vohsen, A. Wood, J. Horowitz, J. Orozco-Juarbe, N. Pittoors, D. Morrissey, C.F. Vaga, C.M. Hansel, A.G. Collins, A.M. Quattrini, S. Herrera. *In review*. Accounting for intra and intergenomic sequence variation in reference barcodes improves eDNA metabarcoding biodiversity assessment. *Molecular Ecology Resources*.

Cobo M.C., C. Breusing, A.M. Quattrini, S. Herrera, E.E. Strong (2025) First Solenogastres (Mollusca, Aplacophora) from Puerto Rico: descriptions of two new species and notes on their coral hosts. *Zookeys*. 1261: 115-140. <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.1261.164889>

Vaga C.F., S. Cairns, L. McCartin, S. Herrera, M.V. Kitahara, A.M. Quattrini (2025) Phylogenomic supports transfer of the reef-builder *Madrepora carolina* and genus *Thalamophyllia* (Anthozoa, Scleractinia) to the family Agariciidae. *Marine Biodiversity*. 55, 69. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12526-025-01552-x>

3 Appendix

3.1 Science Party Information

Scientist	Institution
Colleen Hansel	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Juanita Carballeira	University of Puerto Rico
Leira Centeno Mejias	University of Puerto Rico
Biajani Gonzalez-Torres	University of Puerto Rico
Erica Herrera	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Santiago Herrera	Lehigh University
Cathrine Hernandez Rodriguez	University of Puerto Rico
Jeremy Horowitz	Smithsonian Institution
Syrmalenia Kotronaki	Lehigh University
Kate Lane	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Jose Martinez Ortiz	University of Puerto Rico

Scientist	Institution
Don Martocello	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Jennifer Necker	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Jose Martinez Ortiz	University of Puerto Rico
Luke McCartin	Lehigh University
William Pardis	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Nicole Pittoors	Lehigh University
Andrea M. Quattrini	Smithsonian Institution
Eric Ryberg	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Yanelle Silva	University of Puerto Rico
Lina Taenzer	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Ann Tarrant	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Samuel Vohsen	Lehigh University
Scott Wankel	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution

3.2 Conferences/Presentations/Posters

McGillis, A.S., K. Lane, S. Herrera, L. McCartin, A. Quattrini, C. Leal, A. Colins, C.M. Hansel. 2024. Bioactive secondary metabolite production by marine fungi associated with mesophotic and deep-sea marine sponges. AGU 2024 Fall Meeting

Luke J. McCartin, Annemarie Wood, Samuel A. Vohsen, Jeremy Horowitz, Allen Collins, Colleen Hansel, Andrea Quattrini, and Santiago Herrera. 2025. Characterizing the Biodiversity and Bathymetric Distributions of Caribbean Deep-Sea Corals through eDNA. Deep Sea Biology Symposium (Hong Kong).

Lane, K.R. 2025. Deep-sea sponges harbor lineage-specific and functionally diverse microbiomes. WHOI Biology Department Seminar.

3.3 Student Projects, Thesis, and Dissertations

K.R. Lane, 2026. Microbial diversity and activity across redox boundaries. MIT-WHOI Joint Program PhD Thesis (ongoing; estimated defense date in summer 2026)

A.S. McGillis. 2024. Bioactive secondary metabolite production by marine fungi associated with mesophotic and deep-sea marine sponges. WHOI Summer Student Fellowship Report.

3.4 Cruise Records

During the cruise, the team made five cruise blog posts that described various aspects of the research. All cruise logs were written in English and Spanish.

- **Deep sea corals:** <https://schmidtocean.org/cruise-log-post/coral-reefs-our-oceans-bastions/>
- **Ocean sensors:** <https://schmidtocean.org/cruise-log-post/engineering-ocean-sensors/>
- **Reactive oxygen species:** <https://schmidtocean.org/cruise-log-post/the-importance-of-reactive-oxygen-species/>
- **Coral health diagnostics:** <https://schmidtocean.org/cruise-log-post/reactive-protection-video-update/>
- **ROS and life:** <https://schmidtocean.org/cruise-log-post/assessing-deep-coral-health/>
- A post-cruise permit report was also submitted in Spring 2024 to [Departamento de Recursos Naturales y Ambientales: DRNA](#).

3.5 Media

- [Scientists use new Technology to examine health of deep-sea corals, find suspected new species.](#)
- [Transparent deep sea creature with ‘flashing lights’ stuns people](#)
- [Expedition Taps New Tech to Check Deep-sea Coral Health](#)

3.6 Community Outreach

The team collaborated with game developers at subROV to add SOLARIS and ROS measurements as part of the tools and missions for gamers. This activity introduces deep-sea enthusiasts and gamers to science and technology. See <https://sqr3lab.com/subrov/>. This activity also initiated a new collaboration between WHOI and subROV to add further WHOI assets to the game.

Over 300 individual samples comprising 75+ species of corals and sponges were collected. A fragment of each is being archived in museums in Puerto Rico and at the Smithsonian NMNH. Larger specimens were also collected for display at museums in Puerto Rico via collaboration with scientists at the University of Puerto Rico.

Six students from the University of Puerto Rico joined the cruise. All but one of the students had never been on a research cruise previously.